

Readability Analysis of Orthodontic Treatment Information Texts on Dentistry Faculties' Websites

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ABSTRACT

This study assesses the readability of patient information on orthodontic department websites at dentistry faculties in Turkey and Northern Cyprus. A total of 101 university websites were reviewed. The informative texts from 68 of these sites were assessed using the Ateşman and Flesch Readability Indexes. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to evaluate variations in normal distribution. When normality was not present, Independent Sample T-tests and Mann-Whitney U tests were employed for comparing two independent groups. Additionally, Fisher's Exact test was applied in cases where the sample size assumption for testing the relationship between categorical variables (expected value > 5) was not met. The analysis revealed that the average Ateşman Readability Index score is 45.34 for public universities and 38.61 for private universities. The texts were classified as 0% very easy, 2.9% easy, 35.2% medium, 42.6% difficult, and 19.1% very difficult. No significant statistical difference was found between the readability scores of public and private universities. ($p > 0.05$). According to the Flesch Reading Ease, the texts were at the "11th-12th grade" level, highlighting their difficulty for the general public to read and comprehend. The results reveal that the informational texts regarding orthodontic treatments on the websites of university dentistry faculties are generally "difficult" to read. This underscores the need for readability tools to make patient information more accessible. Using clear and concise language can help patients understand the texts more easily.

INTRODUCTION

Orthodontic treatment corrects dental and skeletal issues, improving chewing, speech, joint function, and gum health, in addition to aesthetics (1).

Despite the abundance of online information about orthodontic treatments, much of it is not effectively communicated to patients. This results from either inadequate detailed knowledge or a lack of clarity and simplicity in the shared data. A study reported that 85% of patients research their dental problems online before doctor appointments (2).

The growing ubiquity of the internet has, over the years, made information from various fields, including healthcare, easily accessible, thus becoming a primary source of information for a large number of users (3). This situation requires verifying the reliability of online information and ensuring that it is understandable. Incorrect or incomplete information can mislead patients regarding their health and cause unnecessary anxiety. This is particularly significant in specific health fields like orthodontics.

Readability measures how effortlessly a text can be comprehended by its target audience (4). The comprehension and understanding of the same text can vary among individuals; while one person may easily grasp it, another may struggle due to differences in education level or the use of terminological words in the field. It is crucial that informational texts provide clear and understandable information accessible to the general population. In summary, informational texts should be written using a language structure that is simple to follow and comprehend by the authors (3). This scenario necessitates an objective assessment of a text's readability level (5). By evaluating readability, which is a mathematical concept, objective results can be obtained (6).

In readability analysis, various measurement tools or indexes are utilized. These include highly objective systems such as the Gunning-Fog index, Smog-Simple measure, ARI-automated readability index, and Flesch-Kincaid value. Additionally, the Ateşman readability index is a formula system developed to suit the Turkish language, which evaluates average word and sentence lengths (7, 8).

It is crucial for the informational texts in this field on university websites to be easily understandable and readable. Therefore, this research seeks to evaluate and contrast the readability of informational texts available on the websites of orthodontic departments within university dentistry faculties.

METHODS

This study took place on January 28-29, 2025, utilizing data from the official websites of dentistry faculties (9). We examined 101 dentistry faculties listed in the Higher Education Institution's university atlas, categorizing them into public and private universities.

The readability levels were assessed using the Ateşman readability formula (10). The Ateşman readability level was calculated using an online readability program (<http://okunabilirlikindeksi.com/>) and the data obtained were transferred to Excel.

The Ateşman readability formula evaluates texts based on word and sentence lengths. The formula is expressed as: Readability Score = $198.825 - 40.175 \times (\text{total syllables}/\text{total words}) - 2.610 \times (\text{total words}/\text{total sentences})$. In this index, scores nearing 100 signify that the text is more readable (Table 1) (10).

Table 1. Readability classification according to Ateşman's Readability Evaluation.

Ateşman Readability Classification	
Very easy	90-100
Easy	70-89
Medium difficulty	50-69
Difficult	30-49
Very difficult	1-29

Another fundamental system used in the creation of this index is Flesch's Reading Ease classification. Flesch's system indicates the educational levels required to understand the texts (Table 2) (8).

Table 2. Readability classification according to Flesch's Reading Ease Index.

Flesch Readability Classification	
Grade 4 and below	90-100
Grades 5-6	80-89
Grades 7-8	70-79
Grades 9-10	60-69
Grades 11-12	50-59
Grades 13-14 (Associate Degree)	40-49
Bachelor's Degree	30-39
Master's Degree	1-29

Statistical analysis

This research presented descriptive statistics for various metrics, such as number, percentage, mean, standard deviation, median, minimum, and maximum. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess normal distribution. If normality assumptions were met, Independent Sample T-tests were employed for comparing two independent groups. When normality was not assumed, Mann-Whitney U tests were used. Fisher's Exact test was applied when the expected value assumption (expected value >5) for categorical variables was not satisfied. Analyses were carried out using IBM SPSS 27.

RESULTS

Of the 101 faculties, 66 are affiliated with public universities, while 35 faculties belong to private universities. The number of faculties with informative texts on their orthodontic department pages, accessible through their official websites, is shown in the table below (Table 3). The table below presents the descriptive statistics and comparative values of the evaluated texts. It also indicates the number of difficult words, which are not part of the basic 3000-word list and can be automatically calculated by the index (Table 4). The basic 3000-word list is available on the website (<http://okunabilirlikindeksi.com/list-of-3000-basic-turkish-words.html>).

Table 3. Number of public and private university dentistry faculties with and without informative pages on orthodontic department websites.

	Public University	Private University
Informative text available	47	21
Informative text not available	19	14

When examining the data results, the average Ateşman readability index for both main university groups is seen to be 41.9 ± 16.4 . For public universities, this score is 45.34 ± 16.9 , whereas for private universities, it is 38.61 ± 15.97 .

The findings show that 0% of public university websites are very easy, 4.2% are easy, 38.2% are medium, 42.5% are difficult, and 14.8% are very difficult. For private universities, 0% are very easy, 0% are easy, 28.5% are medium, 42.8% are difficult, and 28.5% are very difficult. The descriptive statistics and comparative values of the evaluated texts, covering the number of words, characters, difficult words, unique words, short words, characters without spaces, sentences, paragraphs, and average word lengths, are detailed for both university categories in Table 4.

Table 4 illustrates the distribution of readability scores across the study groups. Mann-Whitney U tests and Independent Sample T-tests were employed for comparison. The results analysis showed no significant statistical relationship between the readability scores of the study groups. (Table 4) ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4. Distribution and comparison of readability scores by study groups.

	Public University		Private University		test statistic	P
	Min.-Max.	Mean±SD (Median)	Min.-Max.	Mean±SD (Median)		
Word Count	6-2021	339.51±398.54(181)	85-1603	338.24±424.69(147)	0.012	0.991
Character Count	45-16954	2679.43±3302.67(1340)	765-13211	2788.48±3462.84(1332)	-0.124	0.902
Number of Difficult Words	6-1987	332.13±393.38(178)	84-1587	333.76±419.18(147)	-0.016	0.904
Unique Words	6-1164	226.43±234.65(144)	77-875	210.71±211.78(120)	0.263	0.794
Short Words	1-288	57.28±62.42(33)	7-251	58.24±72.43(27)	-0.056	0.956
Characters Without Spaces	36-14898	2397.72±2862.14(1241)	673-11580	2437.67±3023.71(1183)	-0.052	0.958
Sentences	1-167	28.89±39.21(11)	5-145	29.43±43.35(8)	-0.050	0.960
Paragraphs	1-59	11.85±13.99(6)	1-67	14.1±20.08(6)	-0.532	0.597
Average Word Length	2.6-3.33	2.91±0.15(2.89)	2.72-3.25	2.97±0.14(2.93)	-1.547‡	0.122
Average Sentences Length	2-29	14.04±5.27(14.1)	5.3-29.4	15.85±5.61(14.2)	-1.255‡	0.210
Ateşman Readability Index	2.5-87.5	45.34±16.9(44.1)	8.5-65.7	38.61±15.97(45.4)	-1.321‡	0.187

Min.: Minimum, Max.: Maximum, SD: Standard deviation, ‡: Mann Whitney U test.

Based on Flesch's Reading Ease classification, the distribution of informative texts on the orthodontic department web pages of public universities is as follows: 2.1 % at the 5th-6th grade level, 2.1 % at the 7th-8th grade level, 12.8 % at the 9th-10th grade level, 25.5 % at the 11th-12th grade level, 25.5 % at the associate degree level (13th-14th grade), 17% at the bachelor's degree level, and 14.9 % at the postgraduate level. In comparison, the distribution of informative texts on the orthodontic department web pages of private universities is as follows: 4.8 % at the 9th-10th grade level, 23.8 % at the 11th-

12th grade level, 19% at the associate degree level (13th-14th grade), 23.8 % at the bachelor's degree level, and 28.6 % at the postgraduate level (Table 5).

Table 5 shows the distribution of readability categories among the study groups. Fisher's Exact test was utilized to investigate the relationships. The analysis results showed no significant statistical relationship between the study groups and the readability categories ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5. Distribution and relationships of readability classes by study groups.

	Public University		Private University		test statistic	p
	n	%	n	%		
Grades 5-6	1	2.1	0	0.0	3.742	0.767
Grades 7-8	1	2.1	0	0.0		
Grades 9-10	6	12.8	1	4.8		
Grades 11-12	12	25.5	5	23.8		
Grades 13-14 (associate degree)	12	25.5	4	19.0		
Bachelor's Degree	8	17.0	5	23.8		
Master's Degree	7	14.9	6	28.6		

#: Column percentage

DISCUSSION

Orthodontic treatments address aesthetic concerns and a range of issues affecting chewing, speech, and oral health. These treatments are needed by a broad population, not just specific groups. In the context of disseminating information widely, it is observed that 82.7% of individuals in Turkey are internet users. According to the 2022 Household Information

Technologies Usage Survey by TÜİK, 94.1% of households have internet access from home (11).

Over the past few years, obtaining information on the internet has become much easier and more prevalent for many users (3). Although this information can also be presented in video and audio formats, most of it is generally found in text format (12). Thus, it is crucial that online text-based information is easily readable and comprehensible to its audience.

A Canadian study on healthcare highlighted the necessity to enhance the readability and content quality of patient information texts (13). In health-related research, it has been determined that while comprehensibility levels in readability studies are similar, there is a notable deficiency of texts written in plain language with high readability (14-16).

This study evaluated the readability of informational content on the websites of orthodontic departments within university dentistry faculties listed in the Higher Education Institution's university atlas. The texts were determined to have readability levels corresponding to the '11th-12th grade level' and were classified as 'difficult'. When looking at the evaluation level results, the proportion of individuals with education levels below high school graduation who can effectively use the related texts is significantly limited. Therefore, it is essential to recognize and enhance the readability of the written content that patients utilize to gather information.

The ease with which readers comprehend a text defines its readability (5). The Ateşman readability index is specifically designed to match the rules and structure of the Turkish language. According to Ateşman, the average sentence length is 9-10 words (10). In our study, the average sentence lengths of the informative texts exceeded the specified level. This finding suggests that the readability and comprehensibility of the informational content are difficult.

Upon reviewing the findings, it was noted that 42.4% of public university websites were rated as easy to moderate in difficulty, while 57.3% fell into the category of difficult to very difficult. When the same analysis was conducted for private universities, 28.5% of their websites were found to be easy to moderately difficult, whereas 71.3% were categorized as difficult to very difficult. Although public universities seem to have a somewhat better situation compared to private universities, the overall difficulty level remains high for both.

A similar situation is observed in Flesch's Reading Ease classification. 57.4 % of the informative texts from public universities are above the high school education level, while this percentage is 71.4 % for private universities.

In our study, while the comprehensibility levels are this low, there are no informative texts in 33 out of the total 101 universities. This situation corresponds to approximately 40 % for private universities.

Previous studies have recommended keeping the readability level of patient information resources within the 6th to 8th grade range.(17-20) While scientific terms are necessary, orthodontic information can be written in a clearer, more readable way. Content written without considering average education levels can affect patients' access to information in terms of readability

Literature highlights that informational texts should be composed of short sentences and words (18). Short and simple syllables in Turkish are much easier to understand (21). In our study, the long sentences in the informative texts examined could have contributed to the low readability scores. For public universities, the sentence length was 14.04±5.27, while for private universities, this figure was 15.85±5.61.

This study excluded criteria such as font, size, color of texts, and website design. Additionally, since websites are frequently updated, the sources obtained within a specific timeframe can change. Future research should explore the impact of different readability improvement strategies on patient comprehension and engagement. Studies could also investigate the effectiveness of multimedia formats, such as videos and infographics, in enhancing the readability and understanding of orthodontic information. Additionally, research could examine the role of patient feedback in developing more accessible and user-friendly informational texts. Finally, longitudinal studies could evaluate the long-term impact of improved readability on patient outcomes and satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

The research concluded that the readability level of informative texts on orthodontic department websites within public and private universities averaged 41.97±16.4 according to the Ateşman index, indicating a challenging level. According to Flesch's Reading Ease classification, the texts were at the '11th-12th grade level.' Private university texts were more challenging based on both indexes; however, the results did not show statistical significance.

The study indicates that concise and clear language enhances readability and aids patients in comprehending the texts. Moreover, clear and straightforward language helps in minimizing potential misunderstandings or misinterpretations of medical information.

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